

Two Work-in-Progress Documents:

1. A Preview of 2. “An Introduction to Fundamental Principles of Dynamic Real-Time Systems”

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Prologue

This is a work-in-progress preview of my work-in-progress book *An Introduction to Fundamental Principles of Dynamic Real-Time Systems*.

The purpose of the preview is to provide early access to some abbreviated and simplified content of the book, because writing the book is arduous, and must compete for time with my consulting tasks.

Early access to some keystone content of the book is potentially important to individuals, enterprises, and society, because there is great demand in various civilian and military domains for assistance with dynamic real-time computing systems—but there is a negligible supply of real-time computer scientists and engineers (especially independent consultants) with the requisite knowledge and experience to satisfy those demands.

Instead, practitioners and researchers in real-time computing systems have limited themselves almost exclusively to static ones.

Fortunately, there is a large body of widely used theory and practice for dynamic real-time systems *outside the computing field*. So meeting the demands for concepts and technologies pertaining to dynamic real-time computing systems has been addressed by:

- application domain (military, industrial automation, telecommunications, etc.) experts but who usually lack substantive computer science and real-time computing expertise;
- researchers in the disparate theoretical topics that enable dynamic and particularly dynamic real-time computing systems, but who too usually lack the same substantive computer science and real-time computing expertise as do the application domain experts, and who also usually lack substantive exposure to dynamic application domains.

The application domain experts almost always hold their dynamic real-time systems experiences to be proprietary. The theoreticians write in the jargon of their fields and publish in forums of their fields. Few computer scientists and engineers, and application domain experts, have the time and inclination to even discover these results, much less attempt to understand them.

Unsurprisingly, most of the resulting dynamic real-time computing systems have left much to be desired in comparison with dynamic real-time systems outside the computing field.

This book seeks to help bridge at least part of that gulf using a combination of both innovative and extant principles from both sides—together with my decades of hard won personal experience (some good and some not so) contributing to state of the art dynamic real-time (including but not limited to computing) systems.

The book takes a systematic (with limited formalisms) approach, using first principles, mental models, and a conceptual framework, to facilitate reasoning about the topic and its constituent sub-topics. That approach is valuable for even conventional static real-time computing systems, and essential for dynamic ones.

I do not imagine that my paradigm for dynamic real-time computing (and other) systems is the only possible or feasible one, much less for all or even most real-time applications. It is one I initially devised [], is the most extensive one I am aware of in either public or proprietary use, and one that has been successfully applied to various wickedly dynamic (e.g., military combat) real-time systems for many years.

It has recently been the focus of a much-needed second decade of academic Ph.D. research to further develop it since my original creation (my co-authors and I published over 100 scholarly computer science journal and conference papers in that second decade []). The paradigm can be employed in different ways, such as being a mental model for insight into improved use of traditional real-time concepts and technologies; or as a partial guidance for developing and implementing deployed dynamic real-time computing systems.

The opportunities in advancing both research on, and practice of, building and deploying dynamic real-time computer systems offer major scientific, pragmatic, and financial rewards.

To make this preview readily accessible to an intelligent non-specialist (even non-computer field) community, I am doing three things to reduce its breadth and depth.

First, I seek to limit the preview length drastically from the book length—e.g., from an estimated approximately 350 to approximately 50 printed 8.5" x 11" pages. That entails judicious selection, and concise re-writing, of only the most fundamental and easily understandable topics.

Second, Chapter 1 of the preview is relatively comprehensive and self-contained, given that it is just the first part of a preview, and may lead to a small sense of déjà vu in subsequent chapters. My intent is that for some readers, Chapter 1 alone might suffice, at least initially.

Third, I seek to minimize the mathematical and other analytical prerequisite knowledge, by using language that is a compromise between informality and precision.

The book itself is somewhat more demanding in parts. It requires a modest amount of intellectual maturity for reasoning about abstractions, doing problem solving, and making both conceptual and engineering trade-offs. It includes minimal formalisms, such as mathematics used in computer science (e.g., discrete mathematics, linear algebra, algorithm theory) and statistics (e.g., probability theory), that fall within what most college STEM undergraduates either know or can easily learn.

Some of the book's references provide remedial coverage of formal topics that readers may need. Other references provide optional additional background outside the main scope of the book.

Chapters 1, 2, and 3 focus on dynamic real-time at the level of individual *actions*, such as tasks or threads executing in computing systems, and physical behaviors performed by exogenous non-computational devices.

Chapter 1 is about the general necessity for real-time actions, especially dynamic ones, being based on shared *first principles*, *mental models*, and *conceptual frameworks* for real-time per se, and all of its constituent aspects.

Chapter 2 discusses *action completion time constraints*, such as *deadlines* and *time/utility functions*, and expressing those in ubiquitous priority-based execution environments (e.g., operating systems).

Chapter 3 provides an overview of *predictability* theories and metrics, especially for acceptably satisfactory action completion times—including the correct definitions of the essential terms *predictable* and *deterministic* that are widely misunderstood in the real-time computing practitioner and even research communities.

Chapter 4 addresses dynamic real-time computing systems that are based on dynamic real-time actions. Embedded systems also are briefly described because of their close relationship to real-time systems: most real-time computing systems are embedded; and many embedded systems are real-time to some degree. Both dynamic real-time systems, and embedded systems, are explained in terms of first principles, mental models, and a conceptual framework.

Chapter 5 summarizes research on dynamic real-time computing systems by my Ph.D. students and co-advisor colleagues and I, and identifies future work needed.

Chapter 6 illustrates dynamic real-time computing systems and applications with examples inspired by my professional work, using material in the book. Also, examples of others who have employed my time/utility function paradigm outside the real-time field are in this Chapter.

Chapter 7 has a comparative survey of more or less relevant work by others that is intended to nudge real-time computing systems researchers slightly away from their static niche.

Chapter 8 describes the need for software tools appropriate for thinking about, demonstrating, and designing dynamic real-time computing systems, and describes one open source program for doing so using concepts from the book.

[The figures herein are copied from my web site, and have not yet been redrawn for this document.]

"Typically, we think *reproductively*—that is, on the basis of similar problems encountered in the past. When confronted with problems, we fixate on something in our past that has worked before. We ask, "What have I been taught in life, education or work on how to solve the problem?" Then we analytically select the most promising approach based on past experiences, excluding all other approaches, and work within a clearly defined direction towards the solution of the problem. Because of the soundness of the steps based on past experiences, we become arrogantly certain of the correctness of our conclusion.

In contrast, [one should] think *productively*, not reproductively. When confronted with a problem, [one should] ask "How many different ways can I look at it?", "How can I rethink the way I see it?", and "How many different ways can I solve it?" instead of "What have I been taught by someone else on how to solve this?" [Then people] tend to come up with many different responses, some of which are unconventional and possibly unique.

In order to creatively solve a problem, the thinker must abandon the initial approach that stems from past experience and re-conceptualize the problem. By not settling with one perspective, [people] do not merely solve existing problems, like inventing an environmentally-friendly fuel. They identify new ones."

-- Michael Michalko, creativitypost.com

[Condensed excerpts from] Chapter 1:

First Principles, Mental Models, and a Framework for Real-Time Actions

Chapter 1 begins by couching the concept of *real-time* per se in terms of a mental model in a framework—*quality of service*—based on *first principles* about *latency*.

First principles are the fundamental concepts or assumptions on which a theory, system, or method is based. []

"Reasoning by first principles is one of the best ways to develop mental models that are rare and useful.

Put another way, forcing yourself to look at the fundamental facts of a situation can help you develop your own perspective on how to solve problems rather than defaulting to way the rest of the world thinks."

--James Clear, Mental Models <http://jamesclear.com/first-principles>

In Chapter 1, the primary focus is on the level of individual *actions*. An action may be an executable computation entity (e.g., thread, task, process), a behavior by an exogenous device (e.g., robot arm motion, radar emission, combat weapon firing, etc.), or many other kinds of entities. (Systems of them are dealt with extensively in Chapter 4.)

We refer to the *operation* of an action, because actions that are computation entities which execute in computers are a special case. For example, electromechanical devices can perform real-time actions that are not computational entities, and hence operate rather than execute.

Speaking casually, most people implicitly have an informal mental model that considers information or an event as being "real-time" *if, or to the extent that*, it is manifest to them with a delay (*latency*) that can be related to its perceived currency—i.e., *in a time frame that the information or event has satisfactory value to them*.

More technically, for a real-time action, an archetypical first principle based mental model is that the manifestation is completion of the action's operation, and latency may be delineated with a *deadline*—i.e., *satisfaction is determined by the action's completion time with respect to (e.g., prior to, or tardy after) its deadline*.

A different mental model at the other extreme from latency with respect to a deadline is that there is no deadline, and that *the shorter the latency, the greater the satisfaction*. That is a

simplified description of a mental model in which latency is regarded for actions based on interaction patterns such as publish/subscribe [] (cf. the OMG DDS standard [])

The magnitudes of the latency time frames in both of these mental models, whether microseconds or megaseconds, are application- and situation-specific, and are not properly part of the precise definition of real-time (contrary to wide-spread misconception).

It is easy to think of various circumstances in either real-time computing or real life that have widely different action time frames and entirely different relationships between manifestation latencies and action values. For example, in military defense, the notional alert "incoming!" implies quite different time frames and latency-based action satisfactory values when referring to a sea-skimming anti-ship missile vs. a land-based and land-targeted ballistic missile. In everyday life, a telephone call about your child at school implies quite different time frames and latency-based action satisfactory values when it refers to your child being injured vs. your child needing to bring lunch tomorrow.

These two familiar real-time action mental models as glimpsed here informally but clearly capture the fundamental latency-based value satisfaction property of real-time actions as *timeliness*.

But real-time is not just about timeliness of action completion, it has a second even more fundamental distinguishing property—*predictability of that timeliness*.

Again speaking casually, something (e.g., an action or action property) is *predictable to the extent that it can be known in advance*. Describing something as ***being predictable means only that it is not unpredictable***—but says nothing about how predictable it is and how that is measured, which is essential information for real-time actions, especially for dynamic ones.

*There are some things that you know to be true
and others that you know to be false;
yet, despite this extensive knowledge that you have,
there are many things whose truth or falsity is not known to you.
We say that you are uncertain about them.
You are uncertain, to varying degrees,
about everything in the future;
much of the past is hidden from you;
and there is a lot of the present
about which you do not have full information.
Uncertainty is everywhere and you cannot escape from it."*

-- [Dennis Lindley](#), *Understanding Uncertainty*

Predictability is a vastly deeper subject than thought and (mis)used by the real-time computing communities, as synopsised in Chapter 3. It is also deeper than covered even in advanced courses on probability, in part because so much is within the philosophy of probability and predictability. []

Predictability is an *expanse*, as a first principle. There are multiple different predictability theories, each theory having a metric for measuring predictability, and thus a minimum and a maximum predictability end-point.

The theory everyone has at least an intuitive mental model of is the *frequentist* one (cf. the probability that a flipped fair unperturbed coin will land heads up). Another widely used predictability theory (actually a class of theories) is the *Bayesian* theory, that employs prior beliefs about predictions. It has become more widely visible due to being used in machine learning. There is a variety of other predictability theories []. Predictability theories and models are chosen based on numerous factors, including characteristics of the system and application, and the type and purpose of reasoning being applied to predictability.

The maximum predictability end-point of a predictability theory and model is always determinism—i.e., the prediction is a certainty, represented in a theory- and model-specific way. *Static real-time computing systems make strong presumptions* about the application and system so that action timeliness can be *deterministic*—i.e., predicted exactly in advance.

Everywhere else on the predictability expanse is *the general case of predictability*—i.e., *degrees of non-determinism*. *Dynamic real-time actions, systems, and particularly computing systems, are inherently non-deterministic* in ways and degrees depending on their dynamic properties—

regardless of any given predictability theory and model. Non-determinism is not intrinsically bad, it can be useful (as well known in data communication network routing), even in dynamic real-time systems.

The minimum predictability end-point depends on the predictability theory and its model's metric. If the theory is stochastic, intuition usually suggests that the uniform distribution has minimum predictability (all predictions over the distribution interval are equally likely). However, that intuition leads to fatal problems with the frequentist theory of probability, and lead to the development of alternative theories, as described in Chapter 3.

Ideally, required or acceptably satisfactory action timeliness and predictability of action timeliness would be achieved by analytically based design and implementation. That might be possible with the special case of static real-time actions based on suitably strong, and often unrealistic, presumptions. In the general case of dynamic real-time actions inherent non-determinism makes closed form analytic expressions for exact design and implementation decisions either not be computationally feasible or not be known. Thus, heuristic solutions to feasible and acceptable satisfaction of timeliness and predictability of timeliness are necessary, and in certain cases can be as close to optimal as desired.

Timeliness and predictability of timeliness are independent in principle and usually in practice. Generally, they must be reasoned about methodologically if not formally to engineer trade-offs and compromises with one another in application- and situation- specific manners. For example, timeliness may be very satisfactory but only a specified percentage of the time; or timeliness may be a specified amount less satisfactory but consistently all of the time. Specifics are discussed in Chapter 3.

Because in general, action timeliness and predictability of timeliness are expanses and not binary, a framework is needed to define and communicate about principles for these two foundational (and other subsidiary) properties. That facilitates being able to reason as a scientific and engineering endeavor about them, to acceptably satisfy a dynamic application's needs.

Chapter 1 of the book cogently and formally defines those principles as part of a systematic framework for real-time actions. The framework is a unified one in which dynamic real-time is the general case, and static real-time is a special case of it. The framework is extended from actions to real-time systems and computing systems composed of real-time (and non-real-time) actions in Chapter 4. The framework for real-time actions and systems in this book is based on the concept of *quality of service* (QoS).

Quality of service is a set of metrics for specifying, reasoning about, and measuring one or more functional (e.g., timeliness, predictability) or non-functional (e.g., resilience) properties of a service.

A QoS metric depends on the nature of the service and its properties, and the service property quality requirements of the service user(s). QoS originated, and is most familiar, in the field of networks, where it is specified in terms of various data communication properties such as latency, jitter, bandwidth, error rates, etc.

QoS can be applied to services at any level in a system. QoS at the application level (or optionally any level above the network levels) is sometimes called Application QoS (AQoS) to avoid confusion with the historical network-level QoS. For example, AQoS for an airborne surveillance radar tracker service is usually specified in terms of service properties such as number of dropped tracks, track accuracy, track quality, etc.

In the framework described in this book, an action is a service whose quality is specified primarily in terms of its timeliness and predictability of timeliness—i.e., *an action is a real-time one to the degree to which*:

- action timeliness (e.g., either the completion time constraint, or the minimizing latency, mental models) is satisfied acceptably well with acceptable predictability
- according to application- and situation-specific satisfaction acceptability criteria
- taking into account the action's other pertinent properties, such as its relative importance, security properties, etc.
- given the current circumstances—especially the kinds and degrees of uncertainties about system loads and overloads, shared resource access contention, partial failures, etc.

A QoS framework for real-time actions is described in Chapter 1, and extended to dynamic real-time computing systems in Chapter 4.

Next, Chapter 1 summarizes examples of real-time computing system characteristics which may be dynamic to some degree, including (but are not limited to):

- changes in the actions and system, including action (e.g., task) arrival times and operation (e.g., execution) times, potentially resulting in transient or persistent overloads;
- changes in action (e.g., task) completion time constraints, such as deadlines, even during an action's operation;
- changing conflicts for access to sequentially shared (hardware and software) resources;
- networks with variable latencies and bandwidths, and changing connectivity;
- partial faults, errors, and failures that are managed during system operation.

A system which exhibits any non-null subset of these characteristics is *dynamic to a degree*. The special case of no characteristics of a system being dynamic at all is a *static* system.

Traditional real-time computing systems are an important special case—the ubiquitous “hard” real-time mental model is:

- small simple highly resource constrained, cost-sensitive systems;
- designed *presuming clairvoyance about the time evolution of the system, applications, and execution environment*;
- all essential tasks have deadlines (mapped into priorities);
- all deadlines must be met for the system to operate correctly.

Obviously those are very strong, and generally unrealistic, presumptions.

System models for dynamic and static systems, and metrics for how dynamic a characteristic and system is—essential for reasoning about dynamics—are covered in Chapter 4 of the book.

Actions, systems, and computing systems, having various dynamic characteristics are well known outside the context of real-time computing. Managing, and exploiting, their dynamics is a long-established research and development activity in multiple different application contexts.

We are interested in dynamic real-time computing systems, and in that context dynamic characteristics constitute unique challenges with respect to achieving their hallmark properties of satisfactory timeliness and satisfactory predictability of timeliness for actions and the system.

To pursue that, it is necessary to address the issue of real-time computing’s mental model (and thus terminology) problem.

Obviously it is essential for there to be a common understanding of, and lexicon for, properties of real-time actions and systems (as for all products and services), else

- buyers and users can’t communicate their needs to vendors
- vendors can’t communicate their product properties to buyers and users
- buyers and users can’t compare product properties to their needs
- buyers and users can’t compare competitive products
- buyers and users can’t compare their needs with each other

Chapter 1 of the book demonstrates in detail that unfortunately, an understanding and lexicon for real-time per se and computing systems has been very confused for decades—probably the worst in all of computer science and engineering—for the astonishing reason that the field evidently considers its fundamental principles and lexicon to legitimately be a matter of ill-considered personal opinions.

This confusion and lack of a consensus on a mental model is immediately obvious by looking at the disarray in:

- real-time OS vendor publications
 - papers by vendors and users at the Embedded Systems Conference and in real-time related trade magazines
 - papers published in professional society (e.g., IEEE, ACM) journals and conference proceedings
 - papers in the journal Real-Time Systems
 - Wikipedia
 - Quora
 - Slashdot
 - linuxdevices.com
 - dictionaries
 - etc.
-

Justice Potter Stewart said

“Hard-core pornography” is hard to define, but I know it when I see it.

Most of the real-time computing systems practitioner community says

“real-time computing,” “hard,” “soft,” “predictable,” deterministic” ... is hard to define, but I know it when I see it.

Chapter 1 also explains the sociological and technological circumstances that led to that deplorable situation, and why it persists despite the drastic limitations it imposes on what real-time computing systems can be built, and their cost-effectiveness. (None of that is included in this excerpt.)

Chapters 2 and 3 of my book offer a remedy to this confusion by providing a concise yet complete and precise first principle-based mental model of the two primary foundations of real-

time per se, and real-time actions (and systems in Chapter 4): 1) satisfactory completion time constraints; and 2) satisfactory predictability of completion times.

Some of this information (e.g., deadlines, predictability) is well-known in fields outside of real-time computing systems. My generalizations arose from extensive successful experiences building complex dynamic real-time systems (e.g., for military warfare applications) with necessarily unconventional concepts and techniques, where conventional ones were either inapplicable or counter-productive.

[Condensed excerpts from] Chapter 2: Action Time Constraints

Systems are comprised of what the book calls *actions*. In the computing field, actions are typically computation execution entities such as threads, or tasks, or processes. In other fields, actions include mechanical motions by robots or factory entities such as machine tools, military weapons firing or launching, etc. To deal with systems, it is necessary to first address the lower level abstraction of actions.

Chapter 2 of the book explains *timeliness* for real-time actions and systems that are based on actions having *completion time constraints* (such as *deadlines*).

A completion time constraint (such as a deadline) expresses an action's *urgency*. Urgency is one of generally multiple criteria needed for satisfying concurrently ready actions' timeliness requirements.

Since an application's inherent action deadlines are explicitly or implicitly critical to the design of real-time systems, Chapter 2 presents a mental model of time constraints in general, beginning with deadlines. It reveals properties about deadlines that are little known in the real-time computing context, and generalizes deadlines to completion time constraints. It describes how that generalized paradigm vastly increases the possible cost-effectiveness and applicability of complex dynamic real-time actions and thus systems and their applications. Such actions and systems are the general, and most common, case. *Real-time actions are more expressive and powerful in general than is presumed in the real-time computing research and practitioner communities.*

Everyone has an intuitive naïve idea what an action deadline is—a time before or at which completing the action (meeting the deadline) is preferable to after which completing the action (missing the deadline) []. This is the casual limited perception of an action being a real-time one [].

Almost no real-time operating systems (except CMU et al.'s Alpha []) and other system infrastructures (except the OMG Real-Time CORBA standard []) directly support action deadlines as an optional first class programming abstraction. They provide only a limited priority mechanism for *sequencing* (e.g., *scheduling*) [] as virtually all operating systems do. So these application deadlines are mapped onto action priorities []. In non-trivial systems, that is usually a difficult and very lossy mapping (an NP-hard problem in general []), as described in Chapter 2. Consequently, real-time systems that are more dynamic and larger scale tend to have baroque priority structures. Also, their priority-based sequencing algorithms are either exceptionally contorted, or very simple and applied in ways that distort and artificially complicate the application and the action sequencing.

Actions usually also have *relative importance*, which is orthogonal to their urgency—both must be part of the action sequencing optimality (more generally, satisficing) criteria. *Urgency and importance almost always must be traded off against one another* (analogous to trading off the return on an investment, vs. the safety against loss of an investment), as seen in the discussion of sequencing in Chapter 4 about conventional real-time and dynamic real-time systems.

A deadline can be relative either to the action's arrival (or release) time, or to absolute physical (i.e., so-called wall clock) time. Both of these are commonly used, and it is easy to think of examples. For instance: a deadline for controlling a mechanical motion (such as of a machine part, or a robot movement) is invariably relative to when the action begins making the motion; a deadline for having a communication with a landed planetary spacecraft depends on the radio horizons of the remote planet, and thus is relative to the fixed orbital relationship between the earth's communication node and the location of the spacecraft on the remote planet—i.e., physical time. At the system level, sequencing multiple deadline constrained actions is much easier if they all have the same relativity. Deadline relativity can be converted either direction between release time and physical time. Because real-time actions most often are embedded (*the converse is not true*) in exogenous larger scale physical systems, their operation sequencing is ordinarily in terms of that enclosing system's physical time.

An action's deadline, herein denoted by t_d , is, by first principle, part of a *scoped* construct—the length of time that the deadline is taken into account by the action's operation environment (principally for sequencing multiple actions at the system level). This first principle is the basis of a crucially significant mental model of a deadline—the most expressive approach to comprehending the general case of a deadline, and to potentially supporting deadlines (and more general completion time constraints) as a first class programming abstraction.

The scope has an *initial time* t_i when the deadline becomes known to the operation environment—in common theory and practice, the initial time is the action's *arrival time* t_a . The scope has a *terminal time* t_t when the deadline is no longer taken into account by the action's operation environment—again, commonly, this is the same as the deadline time. In general, particularly outside the field of real-time computing systems, an action scope's initial time may be earlier, equal to, or later than the action's arrival time; and similarly, its terminal time may be either equal to or greater than its deadline. This is very significant for the subsequent topic about how a deadline is a simple special case of an action completion time constraint.

More precisely, when an action is taking place inside a deadline scope, it is a real-time action. While an action is taking place outside—prior to, or after—any deadline scope, it is not a real-time action.

An action is a real-time one if and only if it is taking place inside a deadline scope

An action's future completion time or worst case operation time (called worst case execution time, in the conventional real-time computing context), and deadline, are most often—in both theory and practice—presumed to be known *a priori* as parameters when an action arrives, by its operation environment (for example, a computer operating system sequencer), and the environment's designers or users.

In traditional static real-time computing, off-line admission control makes assumption-based decisions about whether an action will meet its deadline []. Almost always in the context of real-time computing (but not in principle), the scope encompasses the entire action's existence—meaning that if it misses its deadline, it is terminated.

A real-time action that arrives with a deadline parameter whose scope, and action existence, is from arrival to deadline

Alternatively, and more expressively and generally applicable, an action's deadline may dynamically arise or change during its operation. This dynamic case usually occurs due to exigencies in the application—e.g., change of a meeting's start time, change in direction by a hostile missile, and obvious other incidents in any particular application or environment.

An action that arrives without a deadline, then dynamically declares a deadline scope that continues beyond the deadline

For example, a computational task may declare a deadline scope initiation (and hence deadline) with a system call to its execution environment, which at the system level is a sequencing event. The terminal time is often the expiration of a down-counter from t_d , which is an exception—i.e., sequencing event. Less frequently and more expressively (as becomes clear below), it may be a system call—in this particular construct, for the task action to meet its deadline t_d , the t_t terminal time system call must be executed before the deadline t_d occurs, else an exception event occurs.

A computational task action that is non-real-time until it declares and completes a completion time constraint scope

There are numerous other software-implemented scope constructs—for example, the t_d parameter could be replaced by a variable which the execution environment sets to the currently appropriate t_d . Outside of the computing field, time constraint scope constructs are defined in application- and system-specific ways.

That exception event generally initiates a corresponding handler, which may be performed by either that action or a different action. Either the action is switched by the action sequencer to doing event handling (e.g., a thread action invokes a method on an event handling object instance); or the action sequencer suspends the action and activates another action to handle the event (e.g., by making that method invocation).

The exception handling usually takes place within a time constraint scope either inside the current scope or in a new scope. These are application-specific design decisions. Exception handling is one of the cases where an action might have multiple sequential time constraint scopes, or multiple concurrent—usually nested—scopes. There are complex inherent and application-specific issues, particularly at the system level, regarding how met and missed sequential or nested deadlines are dealt with by the action sequencer. These are very similar to dealing with the semantics of nested transactions in a database system [], with the addition of time constraint semantics.

A realistic example is shown below of an action having sequential deadlines enclosed by an outer deadline. The semantics of sequential and concurrent deadlines is application-specific. In particular: what should happen regarding deadlines 0 and 2 if the action misses deadline 1; and likewise regarding deadline 0 if the action misses deadlines 1 or 2.

Nested and sequential deadlines' scopes have application-specific semantics

These complex issues are discussed further in the Real-Time Systems Chapter 4 excerpts in this preview.

Misconceptions about deadlines and completion time constraints in general drastically limit the possible kinds of real-time actions and systems that can be built, and the cost-effectiveness of those actions and systems.

Fortunately, there is a vast body of more general real-time principles and successful practices—but in fields other than, and little-known to, real-time computing []. This generality has been demonstrated to be analogous to the capabilities gained (e.g., for physics, etc.) by generalizing from algebra to calculus:

$$x = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(e^{\int \frac{Q(x)}{P(x)} dx} y' \right) + \frac{R(x)}{P(x)} e^{\int \frac{Q(x)}{P(x)} dx} y = 0$$

Traditional real-time ideas work for simple static systems but are too weak for complex dynamic real-time systems

In the field of conventional real-time computing, *preferable* is interpreted as *acceptable* vs. *unacceptable*—moreover, usually acceptable is defined as “correct” and unacceptable is defined as “failure.” Real-time computing practitioners use this special case interpretation as one of their various meanings for the term *hard real-time*. The real-time computing research community has near-consensus on this being the exact definition [].

That interpretation is essentially a confusion between the syntax and the semantics of a deadline, which actually are independent.

Syntax is concerned with the bare arrangement of expressions of certain types, such as an action's time constraint (e.g., deadline). Semantics refers to the meanings of the expressions—e.g., what the consequences are of an action's completion time with respect to its time constraint (e.g., deadline).

That popular interpretation of real time is a simple special case, limited in two fundamental respects to a small subset of how action deadlines are used in all human lives and almost all automated systems.

The first limitation is the exclusive view of an action either meeting or missing a deadline. The real-time computing field most frequently presumes that there is no preference for when a hard real-time action completes, if it meets its deadline [].

Less frequently, there is a need to know *á priori* what time (at or before its deadline) a hard real-time action will complete (given an assortment of static assumptions). This is the reason why there are hard real-time techniques and tools whose objective is for the hard real-time action to complete exactly at (not before or after) its deadline—i.e., in that case, optimum preferable—time. In that sense, the action is harder than one which simply completes before its deadline. For example, cyclic executive scheduling intends to cause every action to complete **exactly** at its deadline (which is optimal in some cases) [], whereas rate monotonic scheduling can only cause every hard real-time action to **meet** its deadline []—in both cases, subject to the required static

conditions. One metric for characterizing how much more or less hard a hard real-time deadline can be, without being a soft real-time deadline, will be discussed below.

In all but a tiny percentage of real cases, an action's completion time with respect to its deadline, and thus its acceptability, is not binary. *Almost always, how long before, or how long after, its deadline that the action completes is more or less preferable in a situation-specific way.* That is the general case semantic property of a deadline.

The physics of an operational context (athletic game, military combat engagement, etc.) implies the acceptability of completing a real-time action at any specified time t_c . Completing that action at times after, or before, its deadline generally results in a greater or lesser preferable outcome. Outside the real-time computing communities, preference of outcomes are often specified in terms of utility, benefit, value, reward, or cost []. The worst case real-time action completion time with respect to its deadline may be the soonest rather than the latest, or some time in between.

The standard scheduling theory terminology for any action's completion time deviation either direction from its deadline is *lateness* (as unintuitive as that may seem) []. Negative lateness, how soon an action's completion occurs before its deadline, is called *earliness*. Positive lateness, how long an action's completion occurs after its deadline, is called *tardiness*. Expressed arithmetically,

- lateness $t_l = \text{completion time } t_c - \text{deadline } t_d$;
- earliness $t_e = \max [0, - \text{lateness } t_l]$;
- tardiness $t_r = \max [0, \text{lateness } t_l]$.

The second limitation of this specific common hard real-time definition of real-time is the binary interpretation of preferable as correct vs. incorrect.

Well-known examples where that simple special case of hard real-time is essential include automated control of aircraft flight, nuclear power plants, railroad crossing signals, certain radiology medical devices, etc. Academic research on the conventional interpretation of real-time computing focuses almost exclusively on this precisely defined narrow, but important, niche. That is primarily because the research is much easier than when lateness is included, and no exposure to the majority of non-trivial real real-time systems is required (or usually even feasible)—so starting there can be seen as practical. Unfortunately, almost no research progress has occurred in that community from that starting point toward the general and more widely useful general cases of real-time computing.

Real-time computing practitioners use the term “hard real-time” in a variety of different inconsistent (usually ill-defined) ways, infrequently including but not limited to the real-time computing researchers' consensus definition—i.e., an action with a (hard) deadline is assured to be met if the presumed underlying strong conditions are satisfied. A popular class of examples is

that an action (e.g., task) is defined as a hard real-time one by the duration of its execution—e.g., an interrupt or service response time action is often said to be a hard real-time one if it is *real fast* enough to meet a deadline of (say) 10 microseconds.

Understand that the degree to which an action is a real-time one is properly related to “real-fast” only in the mental model of minimizing manifestation latency (as opposed to the mental model of action time constraint based latency). Some of the world’s most important or dangerous real-time actions have deadlines that are seconds, minutes, even hours long—examples are in the Chapter 4 excerpts.

But only very rarely is “a miss is as good as a mile” (and the converse). Endless contrary examples come readily to mind, of real-time actions *where lateness (in the technical sense—i.e., earliness, tardiness) is integral to the logic of an action having a deadline*. Informally speaking, these are *soft* real-time actions—that term is precisely and correctly defined below, *contrary to surprisingly ubiquitous misconceptions*. “Surprisingly,” because such examples are universal in everyone’s personal and professional lives, and they are immediately obvious. (The examples anticipate the subsequent discussion of real-time and dynamic real-time systems.)

Consider that you are taking your child to school. She is supposed to be at school by the deadline of 8:00 a.m. Many circumstances (at home, traffic, weather, etc.) make it very unlikely in general that you will leave her at the school at exactly 8:00 a.m. Leaving her at the school too early before 8:00 a.m. may expose her to potential risks, depending on the earliness. Leaving her at the school too late after 8:00 a.m. also may expose her to potential risks, depending on the tardiness. Even arriving at the school exactly at the 8:00 a.m. deadline may or may not be preferable to some degree. The amount of lateness (earliness or tardiness) has situation-specific kinds and degrees of preferences, such as allowing her some appropriate socialization time with other students, preventing her being subject to potential harm from others by being alone without protection, avoiding tardiness penalties, etc. Consider the similar case with altered preferences when you are picking your child up from school. Consider analogous cases that involve deadlines for the actions of arriving at meetings with your managers or business clients, etc., despite traffic, telephone calls, over-run meetings, etc.

The majority of real-time actions in automated systems are not hard real-time ones in either the researchers' exact sense or practitioners' various confused senses discussed above. A small minority are, but most actions having deadlines are real-time in the general sense where lateness is integral to their logic.

Consider a notional air-to-ground combat mission to destroy a moving (or starting and stopping) hostile ground vehicle by guiding an interceptor missile to hit it (an actual application for which the principles explained in my book have been successfully used). There are numerous inevitable uncertainties and resource access conflicts (radar time-lines, processing cycles, access to data links, etc.) by and among asynchronous concurrent actions. In an ideal scenario, interceptor missile guidance updates would be transmitted at times that result in a direct interceptor strike

on, and the destruction of, the hostile vehicle. In reality, these dynamic resource conflicts and other factors in “the fog of war” typically can create a diversity of more or less preferable sub-optimal outcomes. For example, there may be either a near enough miss that the hostile vehicle is operationally disabled to some degree, or a far enough miss that the vehicle is unharmed.

Such an interception is only part of an encompassing dynamic real-time combat mission. The mission typically can be partially depicted with a construct known as a battle management kill chain, as illustrated in a simplified way below.

A very simple mission instantiation might be thought of as traversing the kill chain stages sequentially from left to right in the figure.

In many cases, multiple (even all of the) stages are being performed concurrently and asynchronously—e.g., for seeking new, and tracking detected, targets, and doing multiple engagements of individual target/interceptor pairs.

All of the stages contend for access to a variety of resources shared among the stages (and other elements of the mission), such as one or more sensors, communication links, computational resources, weapons, etc. Each of these resources is subject to partial or complete failures, and additional resources can become available.

Dynamically and adaptively sequencing all the dynamic real-time actions in each of the kill chain stages to have situation-specific acceptable timeliness (action completion times, and predictability of completion times) is exceptionally challenging (and, obviously, mission- and safety-critical to an extreme).

Moreover, there are cases in which multiple kill chains co-exist concurrently on shared resources.

There is more than ample proof that attempting to employ traditional (e.g., static, periodic, etc.) real-time concepts and techniques drastically complicates and restricts the operation and effectiveness of these missions.

The principles summarized in my book have successfully been applied to such complex dynamic systems and missions.

It is primarily soft, not the hard special case of, real-time actions that determine the degree of mission effectiveness in the vast majority of time-constrained systems. Complex time-constrained systems often do have a mix of hard (typically at the lowest levels of the system) and soft actions.

Such general real-time cases, where lateness is an unavoidable critical aspect of actions having deadlines, are ubiquitous in military, civilian industrial, and almost all other non-trivial automated and human contexts.

Some in the conventional real-time computing field might mistakenly claim that only hard real-time actions (in whatever sense they interpret hard) are truly real-time ones—that the general case of actions involving lateness is soft (or even non) real-time in one of the numerous vague and contradictory ways soft is ordinarily used. The only rationale for restricting the term real-time to a minuscule subset of the general case is that a simple subset of general case theory and practices can be used.

Another misunderstanding commonly held in the conventional real-time computing field is that soft real-time actions which miss their deadlines will result only in some relatively insignificant (e.g., "que sera, sera") degradation compared with that due to hard real-time actions which miss their deadlines.

Certainly a relatively small percentage of correctly defined hard real-time cases exist, such as aircraft flight control and the others mentioned earlier. However, the general real-time actions in the military scenarios above exemplify the central and dominant roles of soft real-time actions (as simply and informally but correctly defined here). In that sense they typify the great majority of real-time cases. They reveal that insufficiently preferable action completion times in terms of lateness (too early or too tardy) can (and do) result in as much or more damage, such as loss of many human lives, as might the hard real-time special case of an action meeting or missing a deadline. *Unacceptable satisfaction of a soft real-time action can be a major disaster, and conversely missing a hard real-time action deadline can be inconsequential and recoverable.* A sufficiently early or tardy action that allows a hostile (especially nuclear armed) missile to hit a large city will kill and injure many more people than can die in the largest passenger aircraft if it crashes (even into a heavily populated area) due to missing a flight control hard deadline.

Although conventional real-time computing principles and practices are almost exclusively limited to that hard real-time niche, a long history and vast body of research on, and application of, the whole general topic of real-time actions and systems exists in fields other than real-time computing. These fields include formal theory per se—such as scheduling theory, queuing theory, various probability theories, planning and decision making theories, genetic algorithms, fuzzy logic and related theories, to list just a few []—and specific applications—such as military

combat and logistics, industrial automation and process control, transportation, telecommunication, to list just a few []. Almost none of this extensive theory and successful experience has been even noted by either researchers or practitioners of conventional real-time computing—they neither exploit any of it, nor contribute anything to it.

Designing and implementing a system having one or more such dynamic real-time actions is clearly more complex than doing so for conventional special case systems in which all—or what are deemed to be the only or most important— actions must (or are presumed to) be hard real-time ones in either the precise research or the various ill-considered practitioner senses. This complexity is necessary for cost-effective and even viable complex dynamic real-time systems, as opposed to unnecessary artifactual complexity introduced by trying to use the wrong tools— i.e., traditional static real-time concepts and techniques for dynamic real-time systems.

"If all you have is a hammer, everything looks like a nail."
 -- [Abraham Maslow](#), *The Psychology of Science*
 (and many other sources and versions)

Obviously traditional real-time computing concepts and technologies are either inadequate or usually counter-productive for creating and evaluating dynamic real-time actions, much less systems having multiple concurrent ones. They are analogous to dealing with the color spectrum as binary, consisting of black (in the paint, as opposed to light, sense) and not-black (all other colors), without the concepts and lexicon for describing and using the not-black colors.

Concepts and techniques that deal only with the paint color black cannot deal with all the other paint colors.

The expressiveness of action earliness and tardiness is limited by the fact that they are one-dimensional and linear. Thus, they cannot relate early and tardy action completion times to corresponding significance—that must be specified with some other mechanism, whose syntax must be added to the sequencing criterion. Reasoning about these dynamic real-time actions (and their systems, to be discussed in a later chapter) requires a richer perspective and formalism that can express the dynamic real-time action completion times, preferences, and consequences. One approach is briefly introduced next.

Time/Utility Functions

*“The problem is never
how to get new, innovative thoughts into your mind,
but how to get old ones out.”*

-- [Dee Hock](#), *The Birth of the Chaordic Age*

To reason about a dynamic real-time action, the relationship between all of its possible completion times and a metric for completion time preference has to be made formally explicit. There is a variety of ways to express that relationship. The one discussed here is functionally—particularly *time/utility functions (TUFs)* [], (originally called benefit [], and then time/value [], functions))—which is one naturally expressive way.

An action TUF is derived from the application and relates the action's completion in its context's physical time to the consequential gain or loss of utility in some application-specific metric.

For example, an action having a traditional hard real-time deadline has the maximum utility of 1 (by convention) if the action completes before or at the deadline, and the minimum utility of 0 (by convention) if the action completes after the deadline. So the traditional hard real-time deadline is binary unit-valued downward step function $f(t_c)=1$ for all $t_c \leq t_d$, and 0 otherwise. The step is a downward inflection point of the function.

**The traditional hard real-time deadline
is equivalent to a binary unit-valued downward step function**

This graphical function depiction is insightful because it immediately reveals how to begin generalizing from an action having a traditional hard deadline, to a dynamic real-time action.

The conventional real-time computing system viewpoint erroneously associates specific semantics, based on two special case assumptions, with the syntax of a deadline—that an action (i.e., computational task) which misses its deadline despite being admitted by the usual á priori admission control (e.g., rate monotonic analysis) has failed and is terminated. As stated above, this confuses the syntax and semantics of a time constraint.

But in general, an action which misses its deadline usually has some application- or situation-specific residual utility to the system. That utility may be either sub-optimally positive, as for action A_1 , or negative, as for action A_2 . The functional representation provides a formal means of reasoning about such cases:

**In general, an action which misses its deadline
may have some residual positive or negative utility**

Residual positive utility is more common than not in human lives and automated systems, so examples are obvious. Perhaps less obviously, in general, negative utility cannot be rejected as contradictory since there are cases where its magnitude is needed—e.g., to make adjustments for either retrying the action or performing alternative action(s).

A real-time-action's TUF does not necessarily have a binary valued discontinuity at its deadline time, as corresponding TUF's for traditional deadlines do. It may have application- or situation-specific continuously changing amounts of, and transitions to, positive and/or residual utility after the deadline time. Referring back to previous examples: tardiness in picking your child up from school, or sending an interceptor missile course update, may have positive residual utility at some decreasing rate, beginning at an arbitrary t_x —and possibly negative utility (constant or increasing) after the action reaches the deadline t_d .

**A dynamic action's TUF generally is not
a binary-valued downward step function**

Without elaborating various possible TUF's here, a representative group are depicted below.

A variety of some representative concave downward TUF's

Note that the TUF depicted in black is the special case of the conventional binary unit-valued deadline.

TUF's that are concave downward (a linear one is considered to be)—i.e., once a TUF has decreased utility, subsequent increases are not valid—are much easier to reason about and sequence, and so this abbreviated preview will focus on only those.

Three linear TUF's merit further observation.

A linearly decreasing TUF can be interpreted as meaning that its action should be completed as soon as possible. A linearly increasing TUF can be interpreted as being for an action that results in greater utility the longer it operates—there are numerous algorithms (e.g., searching) and applications (e.g., radar report correlation) for which this is true.

Linearly increasing or decreasing TUF's

Horizontal TUF's denote actions which have no time constraint—i.e., are non-real-time—but their positive utilities can represent relative importance for sequencing them in a multiplicity of actions. That has the major advantage of managing both time-constrained (real-time) and non-time constrained (non-real-time) actions with the same sequencing abstraction and algorithms. In this document, for simplicity, negative importance for horizontal TUF's is undefined. (In general, importance is orthogonal to urgency, and negative importance is valid.)

Both real-time and non-real-time actions can be managed together using TUF's

Looking forward to describing actions' timeliness using TUF's at the dynamic real-time system

level in Chapter 4, TUF's are sequenced based primarily (but not exclusively) by seeking to maximize accrued (for example, but not limited to, summed) utility U_a for all sequenced actions' utilities U_j :

$$U_a = \sum U_j$$

This criterion can be couched as an instance of the well-known Gittins index [] approach to the multi-armed bandit problem [], as discussed in Chapter 4.

Utility accrual sequencing can take into account not just preferences of action sequences based on timeliness and other criteria, but also intensity of preferences—as summarized in the excerpts from Chapter 4 of the book.

In dynamic real-time systems, it may be that just accrued utility is not necessarily the appropriate utility factor in the action sequencing optimality (more generally, satisficing) criterion. For example, suppose:

- action A_1 can be sequenced to achieve $U_1 = 4$ of its maximum of 7
- action A_2 can be sequenced to achieve $U_2 = 3$ of its maximum of 5
- producing accrued utility $U_{12} = 7$
- and this causes action A_3
 - to be sequenced to achieve only $U_3 = 3$ of its maximum of 15
 - or even not to be sequenced at all
- even though A_3 has higher maximum utility (15) than
 - either A_1 (7) or A_2 (5)
 - the maximum possible accrued utility from $A_1 + A_2$ ($7 + 5 = 12 < 15$)
- which is likely to be undesirable, and indicates that accrued utility as defined thus far may not always adequately represent the utility relationships among actions.

Thus often, action TUF's must provide for specifying that individual actions each achieve at least a lower bound on their maximum possible utilities. Given that, they must also provide for specifying a lower bound on the accrued utility of multiple TUF's.

A TUF may specify a lower bound on its maximum utility and a lower bound on the accrued utility of multiple TUF's

Since usually dynamic real-time actions (and systems) are subject to inherent dynamic uncertainties in their applications and operational environments, it is more realistic to specify lower bounds on individual and accrued utilities non-deterministically.

The most obvious method of specifying, and formally reasoning about (e.g., for sequencing), these uncertain lower bounds is based on a *probability* theory. Various theories of probability are introduced in Chapter 3 of the book because the most widely used *frequentist* one is not the best, and is actually often the worst, for this purpose. However, the frequentist theory is depicted here because it is the easiest to relate to, and has consequently been commonly used in TUF theory and practice.

A TUF may specify probabilistic lower bounds on its maximum utility and on the accrued utility of multiple TUF's

One of the most effective aspects of a TUF's expressiveness is that the function can adapt to dynamic changes.

For example, the TUF below can be dynamically changed in three directions:

1. its *critical time*, defined as the time after which the function's value (utility) will always be less;
2. its *hardness*;
3. its maximum utility value.

These three dynamic adaptations can be illustrated with a notional missile defense scenario. The timeliness requirements for sending guidance updates to an interceptor missile change during the interception engagement.

After interceptor launch, the guidance control actions must issue timely repetitive course updates to ensure a successful intercept. The required timeliness of these updates, and the importance of completing the course corrections at the desired time, change as the distance decreases between the interceptor and the enemy missile, and between the enemy missile and its expected target, as depicted in the three engagement snapshots below.

It is extremely difficult to approximate the equivalent of such extremely expressive adaptive dynamic time constraints using conventional real-time computing techniques such as deadlines and priorities.

**[Condensed excerpts from]
Chapter 3: Predictability**

*“It must, in all justice, be admitted that
never again will scientific life be as satisfying and serene
as in days when determinism reigned supreme.
In partial recompense for the tears we must shed and the toil we must endure
is the satisfaction of knowing that we are treating significant problems
in a more realistic and productive fashion.”*

-- [Richard Bellman](#), *Adaptive Control Processes: A Guided Tour*

The excerpts from Chapter 3 briefly over-view the second fundamental foundation of real-time, *predictability* of satisfactory action completion time and preference, despite dynamic uncertainties.

Predictability is a very much deeper topic than even graduate level statistics courses examine, contrary to how shallowly it is considered in the real-time computing communities. Here there is necessity and space for only a limited formality glimpse of the minimal fundamentals of predictability which are most pertinent specifically to timeliness quality of service of time-constrained (both conventional real-time, and especially the general case of dynamic real-time) actions and systems.

The real-time computing practitioner and research communities use the term “predictability” frequently, with little or no definition, and virtually always thoughtlessly confuse “predictability” with “deterministic.” This can have serious negative consequences.

Practitioners use the term primarily for latencies of non-sequenced actions such as interrupt response and system services. They tend to look for least upper bounds, and sometimes distributions. Predictability of actions' (e.g., tasks') execution completions is sometimes done with zero-laxity time division multiplexing of tasks—i.e., laying them out consecutively end-to-end, from each task's beginning to completion, on an execution timeline (commonly called cyclic executives).

Researchers use the term for timeliness of sequenced tasks, such as meeting deadlines. They usually focus on the hard real-time special case that:

- the sequencing criterion timeliness optimality factor is simply to meet all deadlines of periodic tasks (and sometimes to be fair to, non-deadline constrained tasks);

- the predictability of that factor is limited only to presumably knowing in advance whether or not all the deadlines will always be met (e.g., with rate-monotonic analysis).

Predictability analysis for real-time actions, and achieving an optimum sequence of such actions, is generally computationally intractable (NP-hard) []—but a variety of heuristic techniques can achieve acceptable (and sometimes arbitrarily close to optimal) results in many cases [], as discussed in the dynamic real-time systems Chapter 4.

Informally, something is predictable to the degree that it can be known in advance.

So there must be a process and metric for measuring that degree—i.e., making predictions. In the human cases such as when the action of arriving at your child's school should complete, etc., the process and metric are informal—driving typically employs knowledge-based decision making that takes past experience and current data (e.g., accident and weather reports on the radio) into account.

But many cases—such as scheduling and driving commercial delivery trucks so they complete delivery actions on time, or scheduling missile course updates— benefit greatly from being based on formal (mathematical) predictability theory and models augmented by the operator's knowledge and assessment of the circumstances. Non-human cases, such as data networks, factory manufacturing machines, etc., normally require analytical solutions for making predictions about an action's completion time—whether in advance of, or during, the action's operation. Dynamic real-time actions and systems, and even some non-trivial conventional real-time computing, are in this class.

Predictability Theory and Models

There are a great many formal predictability theories and models widespread in research and practice for almost countless contexts [].

The few models for predictability in conventional static real-time computing systems (such as rate monotonic analysis) are almost all limited to the special case of whether all deadlines will be met, given actual or presumed a' priori knowledge of action properties.

The most commonly thought of predictability model in a great many different contexts is based on probability—specifically *frequentist* probability theory. Common intuition suggests that if a fair coin is tossed many times in the absence of influences, then roughly half of the time it will turn up heads, and the other half it will turn up tails. Furthermore, the more often the coin is tossed, the more likely it should be that the ratio of the number of heads to the number of tails will approach unity. Modern frequentist (more generally measure-theoretic) probability theory provides a formal version of this intuitive idea, known as the law of large numbers [].

Obviously there are many predictions that cannot be made with that model. Individual instances, such as forecasting tomorrow's weather is one. Unlike the frequentist model and coin flips, tomorrow's weather and dynamic real-time actions and systems do not exhibit a sequence of events—action completion times and satisfactions—having a probability function that lies between zero and one, and the sum of those functions over all events is equal to 1. The limited applicability of the frequentist theory led to the development of other, more widely applicable, theories of probability [].

A predictability model better matched to real-time and especially dynamic real-time actions is based on the *Bayesian* interpretation of probability. In contrast to interpreting probability as the frequency of some phenomenon, Bayesian probability is a subjective quantity that we assign to represent a state of knowledge, or a state of belief. In the Bayesian theory, a probability is assigned to a hypothesis (prediction) based on that state. To evaluate the probability of a hypothesis, the theory specifies some prior probability using relevant expertise or previous data, which also includes uncertainty resulting from lack of information. The hypothesis is then updated to a posterior probability in the light of new, relevant data (evidence) [].

The frequentist based prediction model results in the rejection or non-rejection of the original hypothesis (prediction) with a particular degree of confidence. The Bayesian theory yields statements that one hypothesis is more probable than the other, or that the expected gain (utility, benefit, etc.) associated with one was less than the expected gain of the other.

The Bayesian theory of probability is very widely used in many contexts, since so often there is prior knowledge or beliefs that can be effectively exploited []. Clearly most real-time actions and systems lend themselves to realistic initial prior probabilities of satisfactory action completion times, and to providing updated data for revised probabilities.

An even more realistic model for making predictions about the completion times and satisfactions of dynamic real-time actions is based on the *Dempster-Shafer* theory of probability [].

Dempster–Shafer theory is a generalization of the Bayesian theory. Belief functions base degrees of belief (or confidence, or trust) on:

- obtaining degrees of belief for one question from subjective probabilities for other related questions;
- Dempster's rule for combining such degrees of belief when they are based on independent items of evidence.

The degree of belief in a hypothesis depends primarily upon the number of answers (to the related questions) containing the hypothesis, and the subjective probability of each answer. Probability values are assigned to sets of possibilities rather than single datums—their appeal rests on the fact they naturally encode evidence in favor of hypotheses. The degrees of belief themselves may or may not have the mathematical properties of probabilities; how much they differ depends on how closely the questions are related.

The Dempster-Shafer theory of probability is very widely used (as is the Bayesian theory), to exploit prior beliefs—but it better accommodates multiple sources and kinds of prior information (such as for performing sensor fusion for warfare, self-driving vehicles, etc.). It is particularly well-suited to predictability of dynamic real-time action completion times and satisfactions, because such systems are complex and do have multiple sources and kinds of prior information and hypotheses to utilize [].

There remain other useful predictability models omitted here for brevity, given that two well-known subjective models well-suited to dynamic real-time actions and systems have been introduced. They include, but are not limited to, Imprecise Probability theory, Possibility theory, Plausibility theory, Certainty Factors, Quantum theory, etc. [].

It must be noted that some dynamic real-time actions and systems are so dynamic that they are non-stochastic. They have properties that are so

- intermittent
- irregular
- interdependent
- co-evolving
- competitive
- non-linear

that stochastic and other probability theories of predictability for them are either unknown or computationally intractable. Reasoning about the timeliness of such systems is typically

performed using simulation models or extensional (rule-based) and other models from fields such machine learning, decision theory, etc. []. These cases are outside the scope of this preview from Chapter 3.

Probability Metrics and Determinism

Above we stated that informally, something is predictable to the degree that it can be known in advance. So there must be a model of that something, and a metric for measuring that degree—i.e., making predictions about it. We have briefly overviewed the common frequentist theory of predictability, and two alternatives (Bayesian, Dempster-Shafer) which are far superior for making predictions about dynamic real-time actions and systems.

Next, book Chapter 3 summarizes the issue of predictability metrics.

First, of course our attention is on the topic of formal predictability, excluding the other contexts in which determinism in particular plays a role—notably philosophy (human free will, etc.).

There is an all but universal serious misunderstanding within the real-time practitioner and research communities confusing *predictability* with *determinism* and *deterministic*—seemingly without giving the issue any thought, much less having any understanding of probability theories or other formal metrics for predictability.

*"I expose these contradictions
so that they may excite susceptible minds of my readers to search for truth,
and that these contradictions may render their minds more penetrating
as the effect of that search."*

-- [Peter Abelard](#), *Sic et Non*

A first principle of predictability is that it is an *expanse*. One end-point is maximum predictability—i.e., *deterministic* (known with absolute certainty). The other end-point is minimum predictability (which is *maximum non-determinism*). The rest of the continuum is *degrees of predictability* (degrees of non-determinism). A metric for predictability (or non-determinism) depends on the particular predictability model appropriate to its application.

The easiest approach to beginning to think about predictability metrics is with a model based on the frequentist theory of probability's probability density functions. There is a continuum of probability density functions, ranging from the most predictable to the least predictable.

The maximum predictability end-point of that continuum is obviously the constant distribution—e.g., the action completion time is deterministic (known absolutely in advance), as aspired to by conventional real-time computing communities:

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & x = c \\ 0, & x \neq c \end{cases}$$

The minimum predictability end point would obviously seem to be the uniform distribution—e.g., the action is equally probable to complete at any time over the range of the function, and thus is maximally non-deterministic:

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{b-a} & a \leq x, x \leq b \\ 0, & x < a \text{ or } x > b \end{cases}$$

Not at all obvious at this high level of detail (hence "seem to be") is that the uniform distribution intuition has been formally recognized since the 18th century as the *Principle of Indifference*. But it leads to insoluble paradoxes in frequentist probability theory, which reveal it to be a heuristic that may be useful for suggesting hypotheses, rather than a logical principle. However, the frequentist theory of probability does require that the Principle of Indifference be a logical principle. This contradiction led to the Bayesian, Dempster-Shafer, and other subjective or evidential theories of probability (as introduced above) []. This deep topic from both the mathematical and philosophical theories of probability and predictability is discussed in Chapter 3 of the book but is outside the scope of the condensed extract in this preview..

A plausible alternative minimum predictability end-point for the frequentist theory of probability is based on a model in which the predictability of a probability density function is inversely proportional to its variability. An example variability-based metric is its *coefficient of variation* c_v —its standard deviation divided by its mean.

Using that metric, the deterministic distribution, whose $c_v = 0$, is still the most predictable.

But the standard form of the uniform distribution has a relatively low $c_v = 0.58$ and thus relatively high predictability.

Many distributions exist that have higher c_v 's and are thus less predictable than the uniform distribution according to that metric—for example, the extreme mixture of exponentials distribution has an arbitrarily large c_v and is thus arbitrarily unpredictable [].

In this model, everywhere between the end points on the predictability expanse (for the frequentist probability theory in this example) are probability distributions corresponding to degrees of non-determinism—e.g., about the action completion time and satisfaction.

That is an example of how characterization of the minimum predictability (maximally non-deterministic) end-point depends on the probability theory being used. Non-stochastic (e.g., Shannon entropy) and various other kinds of theories of predictability have their own expanse metrics and end-points [].

This shows that non-determinism is the general case of predictability (the whole continuum of probability distributions except determinism), and determinism is the special case end point of predictability (the deterministic distribution in stochastic and some other theories).

**[Condensed excerpts from]
Chapter 4: Dynamic Real-Time Systems]**

The most fundamental principles of real-time can be, and for simplicity, were, briefly summarized for individual actions in excerpts from Chapters 1,2 and 3.

Chapter 4 deals with the essence of what exactly constitutes a real-time system. Embedded systems are also described.

[To be continued...]

Preview of Section 4.5 Embedded Systems

Prologue to this Section's preview

This book Section (and preview) is not a tutorial about embedded systems. Instead, it describes embedded systems in terms based on first principles and mental models (as for other topics in the rest of the book). That emphasizes there is a ubiquitous unspoken assumption that embedded systems are physically and functionally small scale in respects such as computational (processor) capability, memory size, operating system, size/weight/power, etc., and are very cost-sensitive. That assumption is incorrect in general, instead being the most common special case of embedded systems. There can be, and there are, numerous embedded systems that are physically and functionally various scales--e.g., have multi-million dollar computers executing multi-million lines of software, and having large size, weight, and power consumption. Recognition of this fact has numerous ramifications on the R&D and business of developing and applying embedded systems.

The reason for discussing embedded systems in this book is the close relationship between real-time systems and embedded systems: most real-time computing systems are embedded systems; and many embedded systems are real-time computing systems. Although embedded real-time systems tend to be static ones, a minority are dynamic (as explained in Chapter 1) to a slight degree.

By "embedded system" people normally (and we here) are abbreviating "embedded digital computer system." There have been, and still are, embedded systems that are all hardware (e.g., FPGAs, ASICs), analog electronic, mechanical, hydrolytic, or even biological; those are outside the scope of this book.

As earlier in this Chapter for "real-time system," we accept for our purposes here the various intuitive understandings of the term "system."

In this Section we address the meaning of "embedded system" by developing a mental model of it from first principles (as we have done in this book for terms such as "deadline," "predictability," "real-time," "real-time system," etc.).

To formulate a useful mental model of "embedded system," we must focus on the need for one or more first principles for the term "embedded" in the context of "embedded system." (We are not interested here in the term "embedded" as employed for other contexts such as media embedded on a web site, etc.).

The typical use of the term "embedded system" is not based on first principles for "embedded." That can be observed by contrasting two significantly different meanings for "embedded system" and hence for "embedded:" the literal, and the figurative, meanings. These lead to different mental models and reifications of those models. Those differences have major impacts, including at the embedded system R&D and enterprise business levels.

The literal meaning of "embedded" is exactly what the word says: a computing system that is hidden (embedded) inside an application system. An embedded system is a "black box" that performs some dedicated functionality for the application system host. The users of the application system might be aware of the embedded system, but by default they have no direct visibility or control of it. As far as they know, the embedded computer's functionality could theoretically be performed by relays or trained monkeys or even by magic. The users of the application system see and use the human interface provided for them by the application system. That interface may include a means for users or other entities to have local or remote communication with the embedded system (performing diagnostics, setting parameters, etc.).

This *literal* meaning is a first principle, P1, of *embedded* and *embedded system*.

Another first principle, P2, of *embedded* is that an embedded system's dedicated functionality includes some combination of: observation of events and state in the application or its operational environment; application

system-specific computation using some of that observed (and other) information; reaction on the application system or its operational environment, based on observations and computations. Very commonly, an embedded system's functionality includes all three of these, performing some mix of closed loop and open loop reactive control of the application system and devices that are part of or exogenous to it. A simpler frequent case is that the embedded system primarily does computation using inputs received from the application system, and providing results back to the application system.

This first principle P2 implies that many application systems include some functionality and devices that are real-time in the sense described earlier in Chapter 4--i.e., to the degree that satisfaction of constraints on the timeliness and predictability of timeliness of actions is acceptable under the circumstances. In such cases, the embedded system has a number of actions, and interactions with the application system, that are necessarily also real-time ones to some appropriate degree. As explained in Chapter 2 for real-time actions and systems, the magnitudes of the time frames are not relevant to the definition of a real-time action or system. Other application systems with embedded systems have only non-real-time functionality with performance criteria such as maximal throughput, and thus almost inevitably have non-real-time embedded systems.

A major distinction between an embedded system and a non-embedded one follows directly from the two first principles of "embedded," P1 and P2. The developers of embedded systems hardware and software usually need a great deal of understanding about the application system functionality and design, and of the devices therein that it is interacting with. Indeed, often the embedded system hardware and software must be co-designed at a low level of detail (ordinarily

the application system's hardware and software are a given), calling for some education and experience of computer engineering as well as of some computer science aspects. This factor alone makes embedded system hardware and especially software more difficult than for non-embedded computers--e.g., desktop, laptop, server ones.

The *figurative* meaning of "embedded system" is a special case of (but not implied by) the first principle P1 literal meaning. It is based on a different mental model that adds numerous explicit and even implicit assumptions about the embedded system, and about the application system, and about the application system's execution environment. Most notably, the use of the term "embedded system" almost always incorrectly assumes that the embedded system is extremely cost sensitive, due to production volume or low cost of the application system, and severely resource-constrained—small scale in hardware size/weight/power, and in embedded system software size. Those assumptions are often correct, and everyone can immediately think of many examples. But they are not correct in general, contrary to popular belief. Extremely cost-sensitive resource-constrained embedded systems range in software difficulty from trivial to tricky.

The figurative meaning of "embedded system" overlooks the fact that they may be, and are, not just only small scale, but of various scales in capabilities and size/weight/power consumption. There are embedded systems having multi-million dollar computers--including multiprocessors, multi-computers, distributed computers--executing multi-million lines of software, and having large size, weight, and power consumption.

Larger scale embedded systems are found in application systems of various scales, including very large complex ones. Such application systems almost always include multiple embedded systems of different scales. Most embedded system developers have not been exposed to this class of very large complex real-time embedded systems and application systems.

An example class of large scale real-time embedded systems in large scale real-time application systems is military C4ISR—command, control, communications, computers, intelligence, surveillance, and reconnaissance. Computationally intensive parts include controllers for the different modes of multi-mode multi-function AESA radars, signal processing for target identification, surveillance algorithms for target tracking, battle management/command and control. Another example class is systems for defense against cruise missiles and ballistic missiles.